

Dry weight of striga plants uprooted from field plots planted to selected rice entries at 2 sites in South Nyanza District, western Kenya. ^a

Entry	Mbita Point, 1990 short rains		Ungoye, 1991 long rains	
	Dry wt (g/15m ² ± SD)	Rating ^b	Dry wt (g/15 m ² ± SD)	Rating ^b
IR38547-B-B-7-2-2	0.0 ± 0.0	HR	0.0 ± 0.0	HR
IR47255-B-B-5-4	0.0 ± 0.0	HR	6.0 ± 7.1	R
IR47697-4-3-1	0.0 ± 0.0	HR	0.0 ± 0.0	HR
IR49255-B-B-5-2	0.0 ± 0.0	HR	2.5 ± 3.8	R
B3913F-16-5-ST-42	4.5 ± 0.6	R		
Ble Chai	7.5 ± 0.6	R	6.5 ± 7.9	R
UPR103-80-1-2			6.0 ± 1.6	R
Nam Roo	1520.0 ± 45.8	HS	105.3 ± 156.8	S
ITA257	1251.0 ± 95.0	HS	73.0 ± 78.8	S
IR47686-B-B-2-2	1460.0 ± 90.0	HS	553.3 ± 811.4	HS
(susceptible check)				
IR47686-13-2-1	^c		489.0 ± 757.6	HS
CV	10.8		304.9	

^aData selected from 40 entries. ^bR = highly resistant, R = resistant, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible. ^cNot tested.

and rated as highly resistant (see table). Entries B3913F-16-5-ST-42 and Ble Chai had light infestation and were rated as resistant. The remaining striga-infested, stunted entries had drought-

like, leaf-wilting symptoms and were rated as susceptible to highly susceptible.

Ten entries were reevaluated during 1991 long-rains season (Mar-Jul) at

Ungoye (Eutric Cambisols, pH 6.1, CEC 48.2 meq/100 g soil, 0.2% N, 1.6% organic C, 98 meq P/100 g soil, 1,000 mm rainfall), about 40 km southwest of MPFS.

We planted entries in 3- x 5-m plots, replicated four times, in a randomized block design. Striga plants were removed 90 d after rice emergence from plots, dried, and weighed. Two of the four cultivars rated as highly resistant at Mbita Point were also highly resistant at Ungoye. Nam Roo and ITA257, rated as susceptible at Mbita Point, were moderately resistant to *S. hermonthica* at Ungoye, indicating a possible genetic variability of the populations. Check IR47686-B-B-2-2 was susceptible at both sites.

Our tests showed that some of these rice cultivars can possibly be used to breed for striga resistance in upland rice. □

Stress tolerance—drought

Performance of shallow water rice for drought tolerance

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We evaluated 22 shallow water rice entries for drought tolerance under field conditions. The experiment was laid out

Drought tolerance of best yielding entries, Tamil Nadu, India, 1990. ^a

Initial Evaluation Trial no.	Cross or variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)
11371	Pankaj/T141	2.3	101
10743	Orumundakam/CRR1	2.2	114
–	Pankaj	2.1	99
–	Salivahana	1.8	105
11522	Mahsuri/IR2071-176-1-1	1.2	90
9866	Pankai/Swarnadhan	1.2	105
	LSD (P = 0.05)	0.4	7

^aNo yield was measured for IET10658 (Phalguna/PTB21/PTB33), IET10717 (Phalguna/Andrewsali), IET10722 (Nagarjuna/ARC5984), IET10738 (IR36/OR127-1), IET10754 (Phalguna/Andrewsali), IET10761 (Nagarjuna/ARC5084), IET10785 (Phalguna/Andrewsali), IET10797 (CR149-288/T142), IET11524 (IR20/IR25), IET11525 (IR20/IR15), IET11537 (CR151/CR1014), IET11537 (Nagarjuna/Magila), IET311374 (CR130-36/Jaganath), IET11395 (IET6858/ARC6172), IET11396 (IET6858/ARC6172), and Nagarjuna.

in a randomized block design with three replications. Seeds were sown 25 Jun 1990 and transplanted on 19 Jul 1990 in the main field in 7- x 2-m plots and at spacing of 15 x 10 cm.

The crop was irrigated every 10 d until 55 days after sowing (DAS) after which irrigation was stopped. Rains occurred at 120-125 DAS (110 mm) and 150-165 DAS (200 mm). We scored drought tolerance and drought recovery at 105 DAS and 125 DAS using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. All rice entries were grown to maturity.

Drought during late vegetative phase (55-110 DAS) and milk stage (125-140 DAS) severely affected the entries. Only six of the 22 entries yielded grain (see table). All six had tip drying to 1/4 of the length of most leaves. The nonyielding entries were chaffy and had unfilled grains because of the drought at the milk stage.

IET11371, IET10743, and Pankaj recorded yields of ≥ 2.1 t grain/ha, and 70-89% of the plants recovered. In contrast, Salivahana, IET11522, and IET9866 yielded 1.2-1.8t grain/ha, apparently because only 40-60% of plants recovered. □

Stress tolerance—excess water

Screening of rice germplasm against natural flooding in Cambodia

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We collected 1,600 samples of traditional rice germplasm in 1990-91 from 13 of

Cambodia's 21 provinces with the help of officials in the Ministry of Agriculture's Agronomy Department. Most of the cultivars were from rainfed lowland fields. Apparent duplicates were removed, leaving 373 new cultivars. These were direct seeded on 13 Aug 1991 at Prey Phdau Research Station, Kampong Speu. Twenty-two of the 373 did not germinate. Floodwater inundated the field 8 d after sowing. Seedlings